
Policy Brief and Recommendations

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ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS AND DISCLAIMER

Disclaimer

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INTRODUCTION

The NEXUS project aims to co-design, implement, and evaluate innovative, inclusive Gender Equality Plans (GEPs) in European research and innovation institutions. This Policy Brief identifies systemic barriers and opportunities, proposes concrete solutions, and issues targeted policy recommendations grounded in the evidence generated throughout the project. Drawing on empirical findings and stakeholders' insights, it outlines policy implications for research and innovation institutions seeking to adopt a more dynamic, participatory, and sustainable framework for gender equality.

Policy Background

Since 2022, having a Gender Equality Plan (GEP) in place has been a formal eligibility requirement for public bodies, research organisations and Higher Education Institutions from EU Member States and Associated Countries applying for Horizon Europe funding.

GEPs are expected to foster institutional change by embedding gender equality into organisations' structures, institutional decision-making, recruitment, and research processes.

At the same time, EU policy increasingly emphasises intersectionality, recognising how gender intersects with other dimensions of inequality such as ethnicity, disability, sexual orientation and socio-economic background, and intersectorality, understood as the promotion of cooperation across academia, industry, civil society and public authorities to foster inclusive and systemic transformation.

While traditional GEPs, typically focused on a single-axis gender dimension, have been essential for raising awareness and for catalysing initial institutional change, they often have several critical limitations, including:

➤ **“Checklist” Approach**

Many early GEPs were designed as compliance instruments frequently adopting a "checklist" approach focused on fulfilling minimum formal requirements, such as appointing a gender officer, producing gender statistics, and organising isolated training events. While these measures signalled institutional awareness, they rarely translated into concrete actions to embed gender equality into institutions' core strategic and operational processes.

➤ **Lack of Inclusivity**

Gender inequalities intersect with ethnicity, disability, socio-economic background, and other inequality axes. Traditional GEPs often failed to address intersectionality effectively and overlooked the diverse experiences and needs within different social groups. The lack of inclusion is at times attributable to limitations in the tools used for the collection and monitoring of intersectional data.

➤ **Poor Integration with Broader Innovation Ecosystems (Intersectorality)**

Many early GEPs operated within institutional silos, engaging minimally beyond the academic sphere. This absence of intersectorality—defined as structured collaboration across academia, industry, civil society, and public authorities—limited their capacity to drive systemic change. Without embedding gender equality strategies into broader innovation ecosystems, these plans often failed to influence wider policy agendas, cross-sectoral practices, or transformative institutional cultures.

➤ **Limited Monitoring and Adaptability**

Many GEPs lacked robust monitoring systems and feedback mechanisms, relying on static indicators and infrequent reviews. This made it difficult to assess progress, respond to emerging challenges, or adapt strategies over time, thus undermining their long-term effectiveness and relevance.

NEXUS APPROACH

Achieving gender equality in research and innovation requires moving beyond compliance towards meaningful structural change. The NEXUS project supports this transformation by engaging institutions in co-creation processes based on intersectionality and intersectorality, to bolster institutional change through the development of inclusive Gender Equality Plans (GEPs). Nexus requires co-design, implementation, monitoring, and evaluation of innovative and targeted actions to bridge inclusive gaps in 9 research organisations and their respective R&I ecosystems. A twinning scheme permeates the whole project - "NEXUS twin trios": partners are combined in 3 groups (trio) to jointly design, implement and evaluate innovative, inclusive actions and solutions to their common Inclusivity needs and priorities. Geographical inclusiveness is also promoted through a highly context-sensitive approach to action piloting in seven Member States and two Associated Countries covering Western, Central, Southern and Southeastern regions

Figure n.1 NEXUS Summary

Figure nr.2 NEXUS GEP Area and Building –Blocks

The NEXUS pilot actions crosscut all thematic areas and building blocks of the Gender Equality Plan, demonstrating comprehensive coverage and relevance across its strategic dimensions.

EVIDENCE AND ANALYSIS

The project employed a qualitative methodological approach to identify barriers and opportunities, focusing on dialogue, feedback, and co-responsibility among stakeholders.

Nine Info Public Sessions engaged both external and internal stakeholders to gather feedback through online and offline discussions, guided by structured questions. Delivered between December 2024 and February 2025, these interactive sessions fostered collaborative analysis and solution-building around the five actions developed by each partner. The resulting data was synthesised in an Excel matrix, allowing for comparative analysis across institutions and thematic areas.

Barriers emerging from the analysis

The analysis of the Info Public Sessions revealed **several recurrent barriers** that affect the effective implementation and long-term sustainability of gender equality actions within the NEXUS project.

1) Organizational Barriers

- a. **Lack of resources:** Many actions face limitations due to a shortage of financial, human, and infrastructural resources. Institutions often rely on short-term project funding, with limited internal allocation for long-term sustainability.
- b. **Structural and procedural gaps:** Actions are often not embedded into institutional governance or formal procedures.
- c. **Lack of ownership by leadership:** Limited commitment from senior leadership reduces the impact and effectiveness EDI initiatives.
- d. **Lack of alliances:** There are difficulties in forming partnerships with other institutions regarding the EDI topics/issues.
- e. **Lack of security reporting systems:** In some partner countries, the absence of these reporting systems -such as harassment monitoring protocols or whistleblowing procedures- undermines institutional capacity to ensure organisational justice and safeguard against misconduct.
- f. **Lack of recognition of diverse needs and weak intersectional integration:** Many initiatives are designed without considering the realities of marginalised groups such as ethnic minorities, persons with disabilities, and LGBTQIA+ individuals. This lack of responsiveness limits inclusiveness and undermines the relevance and effectiveness of interventions.
- g. **Low engagement and communication barriers:** Low participation in surveys, events, or training and inadequate feedback channels undermine the effectiveness and legitimacy of initiatives.

2) Cultural Barriers

- a. **Cultural resistance or scepticism:** In many countries, inclusion policies and gender equality initiatives are met with cultural stereotypes stigma and scepticism. Entrenched attitudes and unconscious biases, often persist in organisational cultures, undermining the legitimacy and uptake of inclusive GEP efforts
- b. **Fear of social shame, retaliation for reporting and resistance to addressing gender-based violence:** These barriers have been observed in all the partners' countries but are more evident in widening countries.
- c. **Resistance to addressing the topics of intersectionality and equality:** In some partner countries, resistance is reinforced by socio-political and cultural contexts. This limits institutional commitment and data collection, underscoring the need for awareness-building.

3) Knowledge Barriers

- a. **Lack of awareness and engagement:** Across countries, limited involvement from top management/leadership continues to undermine the visibility and prioritisation of inclusive gender equality initiatives. Moreover, there is a general lack of understanding and indifference across all countries regarding harassment in the workplace and gender-based violence.

4) Legislative and Technical Barriers

- a. Within several "partner countries", certain Equality, Diversity and Inclusion (EDI) issues are regulated inconsistently across different geographical areas, effectively resulting in discrimination within the same country.

- b. **GDPR rules** restrict the mandatory collection of personal intersectional data (e.g., gender identity, disability, sexual orientation, religion, etc.). Therefore, institutions must find effective internal communication strategies to encourage individuals to share this data. This limitation increases the risk of collecting data that may not be fully representative of the diversity of the population, posing challenges for creating inclusive and accurate gender equality policies.
- c. **Insufficient data collection and monitoring tools:** The lack of reliable and disaggregated data remains a major barrier to designing, implementing, and evaluating effective Gender Equality Plans (GEPs). Without systematic data, institutions are unable to identify structural inequalities, track progress, or demonstrate impact. Current limitations are often reinforced by legal uncertainties around GDPR compliance, lack of technical expertise, and scarce institutional resources.

Suggestions emerging from the analysis

Based on the analyses of barriers and stakeholder feedback on the co-designed and implemented actions of each partner, **targeted strategic suggestions** have been identified to reduce or overcome the challenges encountered.

1) Suggested Innovative, Scalable Actions and Best Practices

- **Online modules and interactive training**, reaching a broader and more diverse audience.
- **Inclusive mentoring programs:** Targeting underrepresented groups in career progression. Structured mentorship initiatives designed with intersectional sensitivity, targeting not only gender but also minority groups. Example: Holistic mentoring programs linking early-career researchers with diverse senior mentors across sectors.
- **Implementing Gender+ research guidelines and inclusive communication policies:** Developing toolkits and guidelines to embed gender and diversity dimensions into research content and methodology from the design phase onwards, focusing internal communication on the relevance of inclusive research design and the positive impact on society. Researchers feel the gender dimension in research is a formal imposition from the EU Commission rather than a strategic issue.
- **Collection and monitoring of intersectional data**, especially in recruitment and career development.
- **Cross-Sector Leadership Networks:** establishment of intersectoral working groups bringing together academia, industry, civil society, and policymakers to sustain gender equality efforts and inclusivity beyond institutional boundaries.

The analysis confirmed that many NEXUS pilot initiatives—when properly supported—can be institutionally embedded and sustained, adapted to various organizational and national contexts, and scaled up in other Research Performing Institutions (RPOs) across the European Research Area.

2) Suggested Strategies for Long-Term Sustainability

- **Embed actions into institutional policies and governance structures:** Innovative actions – such as inclusive mentoring, online harassment training, inclusive guidelines, work-life balance programs, biases training and so on - must be incorporated into existing strategic plans, recruitment policies, evaluation frameworks, budgeting and research policies and processes to ensure durability beyond project cycles.

- **Dedicated funding streams:** Establish dedicated external funding lines and resource allocation for GEP-related work specifying that Institutions need to develop advocacy for allocating internal budgets for gender equality and inclusion initiatives, reducing step-by-step dependency on external project funding and creating permanent structures (e.g. equality officers, monitoring units, etc.).
- **Capacity building and cultural change programs:** Ongoing training for leadership, staff and students, to embed inclusive values into everyday practices and decisions and promote leadership engagement and formal endorsement of gender equality measures.
- **Dynamic monitoring and evaluation systems:** Establish flexible monitoring frameworks capable of tracking evolving challenges, intersectional impacts, and long-term outcomes.

3) Suggested Legislative actions

- **GDPR:** to effectively address the data gap and achieve inclusion, it is suggested to focus on the following needs emerged:
 - Clarifying GDPR provisions and providing guidance on how to ethically collect and process special category data under Article 9(2)(a) (explicit consent).
 - Promoting data literacy and trust-building within institutions to encourage voluntary self-identification.
 - Developing standardized and anonymized data collection tools, ensuring transparency, protection, and informed consent.
 - Encouraging national regulators and EU bodies to issue sector-specific guidance (e.g., for research institutions or public bodies) to facilitate data collection for equality monitoring purposes.
 - Supporting a culture of inclusivity in which individuals feel safe and motivated to share their data.
- **Work-life balance:** national and European regulations on DEI topics more effectively that could reduce the “jeopardization effect”. It is suggested to encourage greater harmonization among European countries.

The following table summarises the results highlighted above.

POLICY IMPLICATIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Policy Implications

The NEXUS experience highlights the transformative potential of combining internal reflection with external engagement to strengthen institutional Gender Equality Plans.

By integrating GEP Refinement analysis with insights from Info Public Sessions, the project has demonstrated a robust, participatory model for renewing and evolving equality strategies across diverse institutional contexts. One of the most valuable dimensions of the NEXUS approach was the active involvement of internal and external stakeholders. This participatory model not only increased the effectiveness of actions but also helped to build trust and shared responsibility across institutional communities.

This dual approach enables institutions to evaluate the internal sustainability of their actions and align them with the lived realities, expectations, and contributions of broader communities and stakeholders.

In doing so, NEXUS paves the way for a new generation of GEPs: not as static compliance tools but as dynamic, responsive instruments capable of adapting to social, cultural, and institutional transformations over time.

This methodology offers a blueprint for **research institutions and policymakers** to embed gender equality more deeply and sustainably into the European Research Area.

The results emerging from the NEXUS project point to **several key policy implications** at institutional, national, and European levels:

1) From Compliance to Transformation

Policies should move beyond requiring the formal existence of Gender Equality Plans (GEPs) and instead promote their integration into institutional governance, recruitment, and research strategies. To ensure that Gender Equality Plans (GEPs) and related innovative actions generate long-term impact, policies should mandate a continuous engagement of internal and external stakeholders, embedding gender equality into the core institutional culture rather than treating it as a parallel agenda. This requires a co-design approach, where academic staff, leadership, students, civil society, and industry partners jointly shape priorities, measures, and monitoring mechanisms. Such a participatory and systemic integration strengthens ownership, enhances legitimacy, and ensures that equality measures respond to real institutional needs while remaining adaptable to evolving challenges.

2) Intersectionality and Intersectorality as Standards

Policy frameworks need to explicitly require intersectional and intersectoral dimensions in GEPs, ensuring that actions address not only gender but also ethnicity, disability, socio-economic background, and collaboration across academia, industry, and civil society.

3) Sustainability through Governance and Funding (external and internal)

To ensure durability of actions beyond project cycles, policies should mandate embedding equality measures into strategic plans and institutional budgets. This includes dedicated internal and external funding streams and the creation of permanent structures such as equality officers, monitoring units, and reporting systems.

4) Fostering Knowledge Exchange and Replicability

At the European level, agencies should promote communities of practice and knowledge exchange platforms, ensuring the replication and scalability of proven best practices across the European Research Area.

5) Capacity Building for Leadership and Staff

Policy measures should encourage or mandate ongoing training for leadership and staff on inclusive practices, unconscious bias, and equality topics. This ensures cultural change and reinforces leadership accountability in sustaining equality actions.

6) Harmonization of Work-Life Balance Policies

Disparities in national and regional regulations on work-life balance undermine equality actions. EU and national policymakers should harmonize frameworks to guarantee equitable support for parenthood, caregiving, and flexible arrangements across different countries and regions.

7) Improved Data Collection within GDPR Boundaries

Current restrictions on collecting sensitive data under GDPR create significant barriers to monitoring inclusivity. Policymakers should clarify provisions and provide sector-specific guidance to enable ethical and transparent collection of intersectional data, while building trust and data literacy within institutions.

Recommendations

The lessons learned from the NEXUS project point to several high-impact recommendations for institutional and policy-level actors.

For Research Institutions:

- **Adopt a co-design approach:** Encourage the active involvement of internal (staff, students, researchers, HR, leadership) and external (NGOs, public bodies, industry) stakeholders in the design and refinement of GEPs. This fosters ownership, alignment with real needs, and a more substantial impact. Use sustainability criteria to prioritize actions and ensure resilience.
- **Create intersectoral alliances,** linking academic actions with stakeholders in public policy, NGOs, and the private sector. Develop participatory models that empower staff and students to co-design and monitor gender equality initiatives.
- **Integrate intersectoral and intersectional dimensions:** Move beyond one-size-fits-all models. GEPs must account for structural inequalities that cut across gender, ethnicity, age, disability, and socio-economic background while actively engaging actors from beyond academia. Promote intersectionality as a standard for designing inclusive actions.
- **Promote replicability and scalability:** Design actions with clear procedures, documentation, and adaptability criteria, enabling other institutions to replicate and tailor successful practices across diverse contexts.
- **Implement continuous monitoring and evaluation mechanisms:** Invest in technological tools for intersectional data collection and management (monitoring dashboard) or establish productive networking/collaboration with institutions capable of performing data analysis to make the activity structural rather than occasional. Establish dynamic tools and feedback systems to track progress, assess impact, and adapt actions in response to changing social and institutional contexts.
- **Recruitment, onboarding, and career progression processes** should be structured to consider EDI topics and meritocracy. These processes should include targeted training actions, data collection, and mentoring pathways that help young researchers develop cross-disciplinary skills. Additionally, intersectoral mentoring programs should be implemented to bridge the gap between academia and industry.
- **Design training and informational activities** that are more effective and tailored to the needs of individuals to raise awareness and generate greater interest in the issue. These could involve external stakeholders and professionals who can share diverse experiences, making structured training more effective and beyond being merely formal.)
- **Establish secure and anonymous reporting systems for workplace harassment** (not limited to gender-based violence), like whistleblowing systems, to ensure the safety of individuals and enforce fair measures while preventing retaliation. Implement training programs integrating these topics into leadership development, people management, and conflict resolution.
- **Reinforce leadership commitment:** Introduce formal accountability mechanisms and incentives; integrate GEP actions into core institutional strategies to ensure permanence beyond project cycles. Engage top management to ensure the effectiveness of the actions and their outcomes.
- **Work-life balance program:** <any programs are not effective due to a jeopardisation of rules and regulations among countries and among different regions of the same country (*Example: in Italy, Regions have different regulations for support to parenthood; in this case, the design and implementation of parenting programs are more difficult for Institutions that have various locations*). Expand the topics related to work-life balance: include many other themes (caregiving, age differences, disability, social class).

- **Development of more effective communication strategies** on Gender Dimension and Inclusiveness in research and teaching content and implement effective internal communication strategies.

For Policy Makers:

- **Establish more effective and consistent national and European regulations** on EDI topics and work-life balance across countries. It is suggested to encourage greater harmonization among European countries.
- **Evaluate the teaching of biases and emotional education in school and university curricula.** This would familiarise people with these issues and raise awareness of how to manage discrimination.
- **To address the fear and shame** that prevent victims from speaking out, the following actions could be considered:
 - a) **Legislative actions by individual countries**, as well as networking actions between institutions (universities, NGOs, student networks, etc.).
 - b) **Public awareness campaigns** aimed at society to discuss the issue and reduce stigma.

To effectively address the data gap and achieve inclusion, it is necessary **to facilitate institutions** to collect this type of data for monitoring purposes.

For National and European Agencies:

- **Foster trans-institutional knowledge** exchange and promote communities of practice around scalable, proven, innovative actions.
- **Secure European and national funding** to support initiatives on work-life balance tailored to organizations and involving external professionals.
- **Conduct external communication and networking activities** with similar institutions to combat cultural prejudices.
- **Increase the organisation of conferences**, including international ones, to broaden knowledge and awareness of the topic of harassment in the workplace.

By leveraging this integrated, participatory, and sustainability-focused approach, institutions can move beyond compliance and toward **systemic, lasting transformation** in inclusivity and innovative actions across the **European Research and Innovation** landscape, going beyond gender equality.

The following table summarises the different types of recommendations based on the category of recipient.

“Excellence in research and innovation goes hand in hand with inclusiveness and equal opportunities — because diversity is not an option, it is the driver of systemic change.” (European Commission, Horizon Europe Strategic Plan 2021–2024, p. 6)

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